

Physical Education as Integral Part of General Education at Secondary Schools

Dr. Kuldeep Singh Jhala and Dr. Jayshree Chundawat

¹Assistant Director Physical Education & Sports (G.F), Mohanlal Sukhadia University, Udaipur (Rajasthan).

²Guest Lecture Government College, Pindwara (Sirohi).

Abstract

The foundation of a healthy, content, and harmonious existence is a physical education. It supports the growth of a human personality that is well-balanced, well-integrated, and vibrantly alive. It instills the values of self-control, self-discipline, tolerance and forbearance, fortitude, and sportsmanship, which empower an individual to endure life's bumps and shocks and face any dangers with a calm, collected demeanor and a smile on their face. The goals of physical education are discussed in this essay, along with how it benefits secondary general education.

Key words: Physical Education, General Education, Secondary Schools

1. INTRODUCTION

Physical education forms the basics of a healthy, happy and harmonious life. It helps in the development of a well – balanced, well –integrated and vitally alive human personality. It inculcates the habits of self discipline, self control, toleration and forbearance, fortitude and spirit of sportsmanship, that enable a person to withstand life's setbacks and shocks and brave all risks and hazards with a smiling face and quiet graceful demeanour. This paper reveals the objectives of Physical education and its contribution to general education at secondary education.

2. CONCEPT OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

Physical education is one of the aspects of education physical education may be defined in different ways. "Physical education is an integral part of the total education process and has as its aim the development of physically, mentally, emotionally and socially fit citizens through the medium of physical activities which have been selected with a view to realizing these outcomes.

"Physical education is the sum of those experiences which come to the individual through movement."

"Physical education is that field of education which deals with big muscle activities and their related responses."

The old concept of physical education as mere drill or series of regulated exercises has been rejected. It includes all forms of physical activities and games which promote the development of the body and mind.

There has been a tendency in various schemes of physical education in the past to emphasize only the physical fitness value of physical education and ignore its educational value. The concept of physical education has been broadened, as it should contribute not only to physical fitness but also to physical efficiency, mental alertness and the development of certain qualities like perseverance, team spirit, leadership, obedience to rules, moderation in victory, and balance in defeat.

3. NEED AND IMPORTANCE

The importance of Physical education as expressed by different eminent personalities are as follows:

Swami Vivekananda- "What India needs today is not the Bhagwad Gita but the football field."

Ryburn- "We need in Indian education a general physical education – we need a conception of education in which physical education takes its rightful place, in which its vital importance is recognized."

A properly directed physical education should result in health, happiness, efficiency and character.

- **Froebel**- “If we wish to develop the whole being, we must exercise the whole human being.”
- **Rousseau**- “It is the sound constitution of the body that makes the operation of the mind easy and certain.”

4. AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION

The objectives of Physical education are as follows:

- i) Development of well-built and strong bodies. Conservation of health.
- ii) To keep children fit and in trim form during school life and ultimately make them into well-developed, full-fledged, wholesome personalities.
- iii) To develop in them the sense of personal hygiene, social hygiene, moral hygiene.
- iv) Development of regular habits of exercise, cleanliness and play and of healthful living.
- v) Development of personal qualities like self reliance, endurance, self control, courage, initiative, steadiness of purpose, and resourcefulness.
- vi) Development of social qualities like obedience, cooperation, fellow- ship, fair-mindedness, selfless service, leadership, followership, sportsman spirit, etc.
- vii) Development of character and personality and the whole man.

5. OBJECTIVES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AS SUGGESTED BY AMERICAN EDUCATIONAL POLICIES COMMISSION

The four objectives as suggested in American educational policies commission are as follows:

1. **Objectives of self-realization:** The realization of self is achieved best through interaction of self with social group in which the individual moves. Opportunities of this interaction are available in abundance in physical education. The pupil understands the basic facts concerning health and disease. He secures for himself and his family competent medical advice and treatment. He strives to improve the health of the community. He wisely plans for hours of wholesome recreation and acquires skills in the leisure pursuits of the choice. He realizes the importance of community recreation. He subscribes fully to the general principle that the person who lives most, serves best.
2. **Objectives of human relationship:** The individual knows that his own health care affects others. He learns that safety applies to protecting other as well as himself. He understands that physical education participation should strengthen and not destroy the objectives of friendship, loyalty, fair play, tolerance and others. He regards other people in the class as allies rather than as competitors. He knows that cooperation is the beauty and soul of life. He gains confidence in his own individual powers of achievement, but utilizes these powers in working effectively with others.
3. **Objectives of economic efficiency:** Physical education contributes to economic efficiency especially for those who decide to pursue some aspect of physical or health education as a vocation – physical educators, athletic coaches, professional athletes, health teachers or coordinators, safety directors, medicine, nursing, etc. Many persons decide upon a professional career in one of the above areas as a result of their school and college experiences in health and physical education. From an indirect point of view few would deny the significance of health education in matters of general occupational efficiency, occupational choice occupational adjustment.
4. **Objectives of civic responsibility:** Physical education teaches the observance of rules of games and sports and other laws. Observance is the responsibility of all citizens. Physical education teaches obedience. Sense of duty, friendship and sympathy for everyone: inculcates sense of responsibility; promotes tolerance, and creates democratic feelings among the pupils.

6. PRINCIPLES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION PROGRAMME AS GIVEN BY INDIAN EDUCATION COMMISSION

Indian Education Commission (1964-66) recommended the introduction of Physical Education as a compulsory school subject and emphasized that a satisfactory programme should be developed on the basis of the following principles:

1. **Interest and capacities:** The physical education programme should be planned for desirable outcomes keeping in mind the interests and capacities of the participants.
2. **Emphasis on traditional forms of play:** The traditional forms of play and physical activities that have developed in our country should receive due emphasis in the programme.
3. **Sense of personal worth and pride:** The activities promoted should develop in each child a sense of personal worth and pride.
4. **Sense of sharing responsibility:** A sense of sharing responsibility in a spirit of democratic cooperation should grow from experience on play-ground and in the gymnasium.

5. **Supplement other programmes:** The programmes offered should supplement other programmes of education and not duplicate them.
6. **Financial means:** The programmes offered should be within our financial means.
7. **Programmes for all:** The physical education programme should reach and benefit all rather than a selected few.
8. **Special coaching:** Special instructions and coaching should be provided for students with talent and special aptitude.

7. FORMS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AT SECONDARY SCHOOLS

- i) Dance and music including folk dancing, classical dancing and gymnastic dancing. These activities prove useful for self-expression and neuro-muscular coordination.
- ii) Organized games including major games like kabaddi, hockey, football, Volleyball, kho-kho, basketball, cricket etc., dual games like badminton, table-tennis, ring tennis, etc., recreative games like relays, lag games, social games, etc.
- iii) Sports and athletics including various types of fields and track- events like running, jumping, throwing, cycling, swimming, riding, skating, etc.
- iv) Physical culture games like weight lifting, wrestling, boxing, 'gatka'. Yogic exercises, and mass combatives based on attack and defence.
- v) Camping and outdoor activities like hiking, picnics, excursions, mountaineering etc.
- vi) Rhythmic activities including rhythm games, folk dances, social dances community singing, Indian rhythmic like garba, tipri, etc.
- vii) Formal activities like marching, gymnastics, mass drill, mass P.T. etc. Special activities like ceremonial parades, demonstrations, flag salutations, singing national anthem, practical projects etc.

8. PRINCIPLES OF ORGANISING PHYSICAL EDUCATION PROGRAMMES

There are a number of physiological and psychological principles which guide us in the programmes of physical education.

- i) There are different activities suitable for different age groups. Activities suitable for the participation of large numbers should be preferred.
- ii) There should be a link between physical activities and the improvement of the campus.
- iii) Instruction for good physique, emphasis on right posture etc. must be given in the classroom. There should be no undue craze for inter-school competitions. The factor of economy should also keep in mind.
- iv) Activities over-emphasizing muscle strength need not be stressed too far.

9. PRINCIPLES OF ORGANISING GAMES

- i) To satisfy individual needs of children, a variety of games should be provided.
- ii) Our motto should be 'games for all', or 'play for all'.
- iii) Regular time should be given to the games by training games like table.
- iv) Competitions should be organized frequently but winning of trophies should not become the be all and end all of these contests.
- v) Western games should also find a place.
- vi) Students should be associated with the organization of games.
- vii) Supervision of games by competent teachers is very essential to draw the real benefit. Such teachers should get some relief in teaching periods in lieu of that.
- viii) It is a sin to spend the games fund on the few selected stars only.
- ix) The achievement of the students in this field should receive due appreciation and get a mention in their progress reports-
- x) Students should be associated with the organization of games

10. PRINCIPLES GOVERNING INTER-SCHOOL TOURNAMENTS OR COMPETITIONS

- 1) The programme of athletics should be organized with due regard to health and safety standards. A health examination should be required prior to participation. A physician should be present at all contests of activities involving injury hazards. The best obtainable protective equipment should be provided for all participants. Competition should be arranged only between teams' comparable ability. Playfields should meet standard requirements for playing surfaces, and facilities for safety, and all reasonable precaution should be taken to prevent accidents. Every school should have a written policy regarding the responsibility for injury incurred in athletics. Arrangements should be made for obtaining and paying for medical and hospital care of injured participants.
- 2) Contests should be selected keeping in view the consideration that they do not over strain the physical abilities and stamina of the students.

- 3) The ten cardinal principles are accepted as expressing the policies of our organization. The athletic programme will
 - i) Be closely coordinated with the general instructional programme and other departments of the school.
 - ii) Be such that the number of students accommodated and the educational aims achieved justify the expenses incurred.
 - iii) Justify the time and attention given to it.
 - iv) Confine the school activities to events which are sponsored and approved by the proper school authorities.
 - v) Be planned in such a way as to result in opportunity for many individuals to explore their talents and skills.
 - vi) Be controlled in such a way as to avoid the elements of professionalism and commercialism.
 - vii) Not be such which will be meant only for the gathering opportunity of so-called stars from different schools.
 - viii) Include educative exercises and experiences for the non-participants and members of the community.
 - ix) Encourage a balanced programme of co-curricular activities without undue weightage for any of them.
 - x) Engender respect for the rules and policies.
- 4) Good citizenship must result from all coaching and from all inter-school competitions. They should create the proper ideas and attitudes both in the name and off the field and should contribute towards fine living. They should inculcate in the athlete a feeling of personal worth, excellence in performance, and self-respect. Educationally, winning is not the only important item. There are to be acquired more important virtues like fair play, honesty, give and take, courtesy. Self discipline, generosity, self-restraint, and loyalty to team.
- 5) All the participating schools shall fully observe and abide by the letter and spirit of established eligibility requirements.
- 6) The solicitation of athletes through competitive bidding is unethical, unprofessional and socially harmful. It destroys the amateur nature of athletics, commercializes the individual and the programme and promotes the use of athletic skill for gain.
- 7) No school shall compete in any of the following contests unless such contests has been sanctioned by each of the concerned state high school athletic associations through the National Federation; (a) Any inter-state tournament in which three or more schools participate; (b) any inter-state two-school contest which involves a round trip exceeding 600 miles; (c) any inter-state two school contest (regardless of the distance to be travelled) which is sponsored by an individual or an organization other than a member of high schools.

11. PRESENT POSITION OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN INDIA

The present position of physical education in our country is far from satisfactory. Some of the drawbacks are being discussed below:

- 1) **It nourished children:** The children of poor and middle income families are likely to remain ill-fed and undernourished. An average Indian parent cannot provide balanced diet to his children. Such children remain physically weak and inactive. The school programmes of physical education cannot have much success with them. They cannot take active and vigorous part in games, sports and other physical education activities.
- 2) **No provision in the time table;** Physical education is not given equal status in the school time table. If at all a period is alienated to this subject, it is considered as an available period and any other subject teacher can utilize it for his own subject. The subject is neither taught nor evaluated at par with other subjects.
- 3) **Lack of equipment:** Most of the schools have no playgrounds. Funds are not made available for sports material, equipments and facilities.
- 4) **Indifferent teachers:** Teachers do not show an active interest in the organization and supervision of games and sports. They consider this duty as an extra burden and also consider these activities as a hindrance in the way of teaching and learning. They do not develop and maintain a strong interest in them and consider them as a wastage of time and energy.
- 5) **Limited participation:** Only a few outstanding players and athletes are encouraged to participate in them with a view to win distinctions in competitions and tournaments. Mass participation of students in sports and games is perhaps nowhere to be seen.
- 6) **Lack of proper status:** Outstanding sportsmen among students do not get due recognition, status or dignity just as the academically bright students enjoy. That is why above average and even average

students avoid participation in sports. Most of the sportsmen come from the group of students with low academic caliber.

- 7) **Shortage of physical directors:** There is a shortage of trained Physical directors (or our schools). The existing facilities for their training are also inadequate. In the absence of experts, the programmes of physical education and games remain handicapped and neglected.
- 8) **Discouragement for girls:** There is lack of arrangement and encouragement for girls. This is partly due to social inhibitions and partly due to disapproval of parents. We do not seem to realize that a girl, who participates in games and sports today, will be healthy and capable mother of tomorrow. Women teachers themselves show open disinterest and disapproval towards games and physical education. The girl's schools lack more seriously in respect of playgrounds and sports facilities. The present position of physical education in India has been summed up in the report of the University Education Commission which states. "We may say there are insufficient trained personnel, dearth of playgrounds and equipment, poverty of students, absence of organization, poor types of programmes, small variety of games, conflict with academic work and inconvenience of time.

12. IMPROVEMENT OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN SCHOOLS

Various Commissions, Committees and Seminars on Education for Physical Education have made valuable suggestions for the improvement of Physical Education programmes in schools- A list of these recommendations is given below:

1. Physical education should be made a curricular subject in the school at all levels and should be on par with other subjects. Similarly schools should provide a period for it in the time table.
2. The programme of physical education and recreation should cater to the needs, interests and capacities of the pupils, and should have carry over value. It should promote normal growth and development, maintenance of health, acquisition of skills and desirable social attitudes and behavior.
3. Playgrounds of adequate dimensions should be provided by schools. Where separate playgrounds cannot be made available for each educational institution, a common pool for a group of institutions should be created.
4. The physical education programme offered should supplement other programmes of education and not duplicate them.
5. The physical education programme should reach all rather than a selected few.
6. The traditional forms of play and physical activities that have developed in our own country should receive due emphasis in the programme.
7. Greater facilities should be provided in educational institutions in the form of funds, equipments and trained teachers.
8. For the supervision of physical education activities- qualified persons should be appointed as District Physical Education Officers.
9. Periodical refresher courses should be organized for in-service teachers of physical education and supervisors. Special coaching camps may also be arranged for them.
10. All teachers below the age of 40 should actively participate in games and physical education activities and impart to them a charm and significance.
11. The existing facilities for the training of teachers of physical education should be expanded both in quantity and quality.
12. Full records of the student's participation in these activities may be maintained and they should get credits for their achievements in these fields.
13. The physical education programmes should be within our financial means.
14. Special instruction and coaching should be provided to students with talent. Special aptitude and exceptional skill.
15. Sports festivals should be frequently organized and sports events encouraged on the occasion of fairs and other festivals.
16. There is a vast talent potential in the country which should be exploited by intensive and planned coaching.
17. Health, power of endurance, physical well-being, energy and stamina of young people should be developed by nutrition and suitable exercises.
18. Standard equipment should be manufactured in the country so as to be available at cheap rates to all.
19. The rules on amateurism laid down by the International Federations and the International Olympic Committee should be strictly followed in the schools.
20. A sense of sharing responsibility in a spirit of democratic co-operation should grow from experience on the playground and also in the gymnasium.

13. CONTRIBUTION OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION TO GENERAL EDUCATION

True education of the intellect can come only through a proper exercise and training of the bodily organs, e.g. hands, feet, eyes, nose, etc. An intelligent use of the bodily organs in a child provides the best and the quickest way of developing his intellect. The proper and harmonious development of all the four intellects, body, heart and soul—is needed to make a full man. It was the Greek conception that aimed at beauty of mind and grace of body. The Vedic and the Epic ages have given special importance to physical culture in providing man, sound physique, and sufficient strength to survive. As the poet Kalidasa says "The body is indeed the principal instrument of duty." Physical education is instrumental in developing strength and stamina for the laborious and strenuous work in life. It works as a great educational force, providing opportunities for the wholesome satisfaction of inherent drives and urges of individuals and groups. It has direct bearing on healthful school life. Through its well-organized programmes of cleanliness, and orderliness develops the aesthetic sense of the children. Perhaps no other school activity provides so natural an opportunity for the child to acquire skill in the basic rules of health. It also centres around nutrition with attention to sufficient food, and balanced diet, growth, etc. It also concerns with rest and sleep in a very practical way. Often these programmes emphasize styles and postures suited to work, rest and sleep. Physical education is a great factor in the mental hygiene of the students. Again, it makes a solid contribution towards social hygiene. Children learn to play together in harmony, appreciating the rights of others and abiding the rules prescribed for the activity. It inculcates a spirit of healthy rivalry and competition, sportsmanship, qualities of initiative, steadiness, firm resolve, confidence, and poise, courage and perseverance in the face of odds. It inculcates in them self control and temperance by emphasizing the harmful effects of drugs. It makes significant contributions to education for leisure and recreation. Through an intensive and systematic programme of physical education, the students are acquainted with physiology and human anatomy and all about the fundamental laws of physical growth and development is brought home to them.

REFERENCES

- [1]. S.K. Mangal: Advanced Educational Psychology, Prentice-Hall of India private Limited, New Delhi, 2007.
- [2]. L. Ramchandran: A textbook of health Education. Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi, 1983
- [3]. Prof. P. Nataraj: Psychology: Srinivas Publications. Mysore.
- [4]. Prof. Mahadevan: School Organization and Administration.